

SPEECH BEHAVIOR AS A PSYCHOLOGICAL CRITERION OF COMPETENCE OF A TEACHER OF RUSSIAN AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN A FOREIGN LANGUAGE ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract. *In the context of this article, the subject of research is speech behavior as a form of interaction for the purpose of exchanging information of a cognitive or affective-evaluative nature in the spectrum of research interests of such disciplines as speech culture and functional stylistics. The article is devoted to the substantiation of the expediency and possibility of improving the training of Russian language teachers working under the programs "Russian Teacher Abroad".*

Keywords: *russian language, speech culture, speech behavior, psychological competencies*

At all times of the existence of any developed state, an important component of the state structure, influencing progressive development, is the education system. A state that has a quality educational system plays an important role in the modern world. Thanks to the developing mechanism of the education system, it is possible to achieve high results in internal processes, as well as act as a powerful lever of humanitarian "soft power" in foreign policy and geopolitics. If a state has an ideology and culture that is attractive to other participants at the global level, then they will follow this state - this is the essence of "soft power," which is no less important than "hard power" [Bychkova 2017: p. 372]. In the modern world, integration is very important for rapid socio-economic development, therefore the need to mobilize teachers of Russian as a foreign language is increasing. However, learning the Russian language is not an end in itself; the exchange of information in the process of intercultural communication is much more important. The main principle of the Russian as a Foreign Language (RFL) methodology is the development of communication skills, and the solution to this problem presupposes the speech orientation of the educational process, which lies not only in the fact that a speech practical goal is pursued, but in the process of using the language itself. Practical speech orientation is an interdependent goal and means of the communicative method, the principles of which are: the principle of individualization of speech activity; principle of selection of speech material; principle of situationality; the principle of relevance and novelty [Belyaev B. V 1967: p. 137].

Based on the results of mastering the course of studying Russian as a foreign language, our students are presented with quite serious requirements, in accordance with the definitions of the Federal State Educational Standard (FSSES) for secondary general education:

1) communicative competencies necessary for socialization and self-realization, as a tool for intercultural communication in the modern multicultural world;

2) possession of knowledge about the sociocultural specifics of the country of the language being studied and the ability to structure one's speech and non-speech behavior adequately to this specificity; the ability to highlight what is common and different in the culture of the native country and the country of the language being studied;

3) achieving a threshold level of proficiency in a foreign language, allowing graduates to communicate orally and in writing both with native speakers of the foreign language being studied and with representatives of other countries who use Russian;

4) developed ability to use a foreign language as a means of obtaining information from foreign language sources for educational and self-educational purposes [Tryapitsyna A.P. 2012: p. 10].

Within the framework of the RCT methodology, the criteria for the professional communicative competence of a Russian teacher abroad are determined; speech competence (development of communication skills in four main types of speech activity: speaking, listening, reading, writing);

- linguistic competence (mastery of new language means (phonetic, spelling, lexical, grammatical) in accordance with the topics and situations of communication; mastering knowledge about the linguistic phenomena of the language being studied, ways of expressing thoughts in native and foreign languages;

- sociocultural/intercultural competence (introduction to the culture, traditions, realities of the countries of the language being studied within the framework of topics, areas and situations of communication that correspond to the experience, interests, and psychological characteristics of students; the formation of the ability to represent one's country and its culture in conditions of intercultural communication, excluding ethnocentrism);

- compensatory competence (development of skills to get out of a situation in conditions of a shortage of linguistic means when receiving and transmitting information);

- educational and cognitive competence (further development of general and special educational skills, universal methods of activity; familiarization with the ways and techniques available to students for independent study of languages and cultures, including the use of new information technologies.

My pedagogical experience of working in an international humanitarian project, directly in different schools with the Uzbek language of instruction, showed that in developing interest in the Russian language, culture, etc., one cannot rely only on the content of the recommended textbook. Under modern conditions, an unproductively small teaching load (2 academic hours per week) and a varied composition of students in national schools, both horizontally and vertically, it is impossible to involve students in active cognitive activity. Any, even the most informative, material in the manual arouses in students only contemplative interest in the subject.

Thus, the teacher's speech behavior is the most important component of both the educational and educational process, demonstrating a model and guideline for the student's speech action. Accordingly, in order to give students the correct example, a teacher of Russian as a foreign language in a foreign language environment needs to organize his own speech behavior. To enhance cognitive activity, it is necessary to immerse Uzbek schoolchildren in an artificial "language environment", setting them a communicative task that is interesting to them in thematic or practical terms. In this case, Uzbek schoolchildren, even with a minimal vocabulary, have opportunities to develop communicative competence in the totality of all five of its components: speech, language, sociocultural, compensatory and educational-cognitive. Widely use involuntary memorization of lexical means and grammatical structures in the course of solving problematic problems, stimulate the development of creative thinking and imagination, create conditions for

freedom of expression of thought and comprehension of what is perceived. The variety of means of expressing meaning brings children into free creativity.

The relevance and scientific novelty of the systemic organization of speech load and control of speech behavior in lessons lies in the fact that, given the existing above-mentioned problems, they allow solving the most complex and at the same time the most significant task for the methodology - the creation of a language environment and, on its basis, activation of the need to use Russian language in practice.

The cultural or normative speech of a teacher of Russian as a foreign language should be: authentic and normative, free from dialectisms, vernacular, vulgarisms and slang; expressive, with an emphasis on intonation means that make speech clearer and more understandable, with moderate use of gestures, facial expressions, and other means of expressiveness; adaptive, i.e. corresponding to the ability of students to understand it, with the systematic expansion of these opportunities. This requirement applies not only to the linguistic means that determine the teacher's speech, but also to the tempo of speech; capacious and concise [Lvov M.R. 2004: p. 71]. The teacher should maintain a balance in speaking during the lesson, distributing the speech load among all participants in the educational process.

A teacher of a foreign language as a foreign language in a foreign language environment, who has sufficient psychological and pedagogical competencies, has incomparably greater opportunities for using the Russian language as the only means of communication between teacher and students and creating an "artificial language environment." My observations show that these opportunities are almost not used in the lessons of our Uzbek colleagues, Russian language teachers in national schools.

During a visit to Russian language lessons in Uzbek schools and an analysis of the most common problem situations in the process of verbal communication, multiple problems associated with insufficient communicative competence for communication in the professional sphere were identified. The result of a survey I conducted among teachers in the Surkhadarya region showed the request of Uzbek teachers to gain knowledge of the normative, ethical and communicative aspects of the Russian language, within the framework of the academic discipline "Russian language and speech culture."

In addition to the insufficient level of proficiency in the standard Russian language established by the study in the lessons of Uzbek Russian teachers, common methodological errors were discovered that do not allow creating the necessary "language environment" in the lessons;

1) the teacher reads or speaks in Russian, constantly accompanying his speech with a translation into Uzbek, which does not contribute to the formation of skills in students. Knowing that the teacher usually translates what he says, the student makes no effort to understand the teacher's speech in Russian.

2) the teacher achieves understanding of his statements or orders in Russian, using only the vocabulary that the students have already mastered. In this case, the teacher cannot create an authentic "language environment" for students, and "caution" in the use of words and expressions that students "have not studied" interferes with the development of oral speech skills.

3) Sometimes the teacher speaks Russian, excessively including non-verbal communication (appearance, facial expressions, gaze, gestures, etc.) in his speech activity, reducing the decisive role of spoken speech.

The results of the study allow us to recommend approaches to solving the identified problem. To prevent and correct typical errors in the speech of teachers of Russian as a foreign language working in an international project, it is advisable to use the results of theoretical research in the field of normativity of the Russian language and comparative linguistics. To diversify the psychological and pedagogical training of international relations teachers in the spectrum of language literacy and readiness to learn and motivation to teach. Summarizing the above, the logical conclusions will be about the need to create and develop advanced training courses in Uzbekistan for our partners and colleagues, Uzbek teachers of the Russian language, especially for teachers in national schools. The educational program should include a certain set of modules focused on mastering knowledge and practices that are professionally significant for a future teacher: subject-based and methodological, psychological and pedagogical modules, and others.

The role of an experienced international teacher as a mentor for Uzbek teachers in teaching how to organize balanced speech communication in Russian as a foreign language lessons is important here. The main goal of mentoring is to develop skills, achieve growth in personal qualities and improve pedagogical competencies.

In practical application, special emphasis is placed on additional study of the Russian language in the segment of the discipline “Culture of Speech” and the development of communicative skills of Uzbek teachers, mastering specific skills in conducting educational work.

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